

Effectiveness And Safety Of Iron Sucrose Vs Fcm Injection In Iron Deficiency Anemia

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ABSTRACT

Anemias are group of diseases characterized by a decrease in hemoglobin [HB] or red blood cells [RBC], resulting in decreased oxygen capacity of blood. The WHO defines anemia as HB less than 13 g/dl in men or less than 12 g/dl in women. Anemia in pregnancy is defined as low hemoglobin [$>12\text{g/dl}$] concentration resulting in decrease in oxygen carrying capacity of blood in pregnant women. To compare the effectiveness and safety of intravenous Iron Sucrose versus Ferric Carboxy maltose (FCM) in the treatment of iron deficiency anemia during pregnancy in Government General Hospital, Madanapalle for a period of 6 months (November 2024 to April 2025), sample size 146 who are suffered with anemia in pregnancy. Hemoglobin (HB) improvement after treatment with Iron Sucrose and FCM. Most patients improved by 1 to 4 g/dL. FCM had a slightly higher percentage (50.68%) improving by 3 to 4 g/dL compared to Iron Sucrose (43.83%). No patients in either group showed an improvement of 5 to 6 g/dL. Patients receiving FCM experienced faster hemoglobin improvement, fewer adverse effects, and higher satisfaction rates, likely due to its single-dose convenience and better tolerability. Given its practical advantages, FCM may be considered a more efficient and patient- friendly option for anemia management, particularly in settings where follow-up and multiple infusions may be challenging. Further large-scale studies are recommended to strengthen the evidence base and support wider clinical use.

Keywords: Anemia, Hemoglobin, Ferric Carboxy Maltose, Iron Sucrose.

INTRODUCTION

Iron deficiency anemia (IDA) is common among women. In women of childbearing age, the most common cause of IDA is loss of iron due to menstrual blood loss or pregnancy. The risk factors related to IDA among women include low socio-economic status, social deprivation, teenage pregnancy, high parity, multiple pregnancies, and short inter-pregnancy intervals.^[1] IDA is the final state of iron depletion due to inability to maintain physiologic balance of iron uptake and utilization.^[2] Iron deficiency depresses the erythropoietic system resulting in decreased hemoglobin (Hb) levels.^[3] Anemia in women is defined by the World Health Organization as an Hb level $<12\text{g/dL}$ in

nonpregnant women and $<11\text{g/dL}$ in pregnant women.^[4] The prevalence of IDA among pregnant women increases from 6.9% in the first trimester to 14.3% and 28.4% in the second and third trimesters, respectively.^[5] Traditionally, oral iron replacement is used as the first-line therapy in patients with IDA due to its ease of administration, and early initiation of this treatment can correct anemia. However, oral iron has some disadvantages such as side-effects, poor compliance, and limited gastrointestinal absorption.^[6,7] Sometimes, oral iron replacement even after prolonged treatment may fail to adequately correct anemia and iron reserves, before delivery in pregnant women.^[7,8] This situation can be easily and efficiently remedied by the use of intravenous (IV) iron replacement, which can deliver the total amount

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of required iron over a short period. Currently, the most commonly used IV iron formulations are iron sucrose (IS) and ferric carboxymaltose (FCM).^[1,9-13] To date, there have been no systematic reviews comparing IV iron formulations, such as FCM and IS, in the treatment of IDA among obstetric and gynecologic patients.

Therefore, this study aimed to perform a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials (RCTs) comparing the efficacy and safety of most commonly used IV iron formulations, FCM and IS, in the treatment of IDA among obstetric and gynecologic patients.

Research Methodology

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was a prospective comparative interventional analytical study. Study period was 06 months and carried out in the department of obstetrics and Gynecology at GGH Hospital, Madanapalle from November 2024 to April 2025.

Study population

Pregnant woman diagnosed with iron deficiency anemia

Sample size

The study comprised of 146 cases which are to be randomly distributed into two groups

Group - A: cases in this group receive intravenous iron sucrose therapy.

Group - B: cases in this group receive Ferric Carboxy maltose therapy

Eligibility criteria

Inclusion criteria

146 pregnant with iron deficiency anemia of pregnancy.

Exclusion criteria

Anemia not caused by iron deficiency

Known hypersensitivity to FCM or IRON SUCROSE

Sickle cell disease

Not consenting

On enrollment, a detailed clinical history (menstrual, obstetric), previous treatment history including iron therapy, compliance with oral iron and chronic medical illness was taken. Detailed examination including anthropometry, general physical examination and obstetric examination was done. Routine antenatal investigations were done according to the standard departmental protocol. Investigations specific to anemia included hemogram, reticulocyte count and peripheral blood smear, red cell indices including mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH), mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC), red cell distribution width (RDW), hemoglobin electrophoresis, serum ferritin levels, serum iron, total iron binding capacity (TIBC) and transferrin saturation were done. After calculating total iron deficit, patients in the FCM group were administered i.v. FCM (Inj Orofer FCM, Emcure Pharmaceuticals Ltd., Pune, India). Maximal dose per sitting was 1000 mg which was diluted in 200 ml 0.9% normal saline and administered as an IV infusion over 30 min (Due to the limited availability of safety data for its use in pregnancy, a longer infusion protocol (30 min) than recommended by the manufacturer (15 min) was used). Patients in ISC group were administered IV ISC as 200 mg (Inj Orofer S, Emcure Pharmaceuticals Ltd., Pune, India) in 200 ml NS over 15-20 min twice weekly till dosage was completed, not to exceed 600 mg per week. The general condition of the patient, blood pressure and pulse rate were noted before infusion and every five minutes during infusion and fetal heart rate monitoring was done before and after infusion. Any minor or major adverse effects were noted. All patients were followed up after 4 weeks and 90 days of initiation of treatment. Hemoglobin, RBC indices and serum iron studies were done after 90 days. Patients reported minor or major adverse events at follow-up visits. Primary outcome was change in hemoglobin level from baseline after 90 days. Secondary outcomes were change in ferritin levels, improvement in serum iron studies and RBC indices, safety and side effects of treatment and perinatal

outcome. Data were presented as number (%) or mean \pm SD/median (min-max) as appropriate. Baseline categorical variables were compared between the groups using Chi-square/Fisher's exact test and continuous variables were compared using Student's t-test. The p value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results and discussion

Age 21–25 has the highest usage of both Iron Sucrose (43.83%) and FCM (45.20%). proportion of individuals receiving both treatments fall under the Secondary education level (43.83% for Iron Sucrose

and 39.72% for FCM), while the lowest is in the Graduate category for Iron Sucrose (13.69%).^[14] Most Iron Sucrose patients fall in the middle-income group (89.04%), while FCM is mainly used by low-income patients (67.12%). A higher percentage of FCM patients are from rural areas (75.34%) compared to Iron Sucrose (52.34%).^[15] The majority in both groups are housewives—74.34% for Iron Sucrose and 86.30% for FCM—while a smaller portion belongs to other occupations.^[16] Iron Sucrose is most used among multigravida patients (46.57%), while FCM is most used among secondary gravida (39.72%). (Figure-1)

Figure-1: Gravida

Normal Vaginal Delivery (NVD) was more common with FCM (38.35%) than Iron Sucrose (23.28%).^[17-19] LSCS rates were similar in both groups, while the

NA category was higher in the Iron Sucrose group (46.57%) compared to FCM (34.24%). (Figure-2)

Figure-2: Parturition

Pre-treatment hemoglobin (HB) levels among patients receiving Iron Sucrose and FCM. Most patients had HB levels of 7 to 9 g/dL—56.18% in the Iron Sucrose

group and 67.12% in the FCM group.^[20] Very few had levels of 5 to 7 g/dL or above 9 g/dL, with none in the 11 to 13 g/dL range. (Figure-3)

Figure-3: Pre-treatment Hemoglobin

Hemoglobin (HB) improvement after treatment with Iron Sucrose and FCM. Most patients improved by 1 to 4 g/dL. [21] FCM had a slightly higher percentage

(50.68%) improving by 3 to 4 g/dL compared to Iron Sucrose (43.83%). No patients in either group showed an improvement of 5 to 6 g/dL. (Figure-4)

Figure-4: HB improvement after treatment

Pre-existing health conditions in patients treated with Iron Sucrose and FCM. Anaemia and thyroid disorders were the most common in both groups, with higher rates in the FCM group (19.17% and 13.69%, respectively). Hypertension and epilepsy were also more frequent in the FCM group, while no cases of diabetes or TB were reported in either group. [22-23]

Adverse drug reactions (ADRs) were reported much more frequently with Iron Sucrose (58.90%) compared to FCM (16.43%). Most patients in the FCM group (83.56%) did not experience any ADRs. (Figure-5)

Figure-5: Type of ADR

Iron Sucrose caused more adverse drug reactions (ADRs) than FCM, especially rashes (21%) and injection site pain (24.65%). In contrast, FCM mainly caused headaches (8.21%) and fewer cases of nausea and pain. [24-25]

The majority of ADRs for both Iron Sucrose (90.69%) and FCM (83.56%) resolved without intervention. However, a higher percentage of FCM-related ADRs (16.43%) required intervention compared to Iron Sucrose (9%). (Figure-6)

Figure-6: Management of ADR

Iron Sucrose and FCM led to overall symptom improvement, with FCM showing a higher rate of significant improvement (72.60%) compared to Iron

Sucrose (63.01%). [26] No cases reported lack of improvement in either group. (Figure-7)

Figure-7: Overall symptom improvement

Patient's Satisfaction with Treatment compares satisfaction levels between two iron treatments: sucrose and FCM. It shows that FCM has a higher

percentage of patients who are "Very Satisfied"(49.31%) and "Satisfied" (42.46%) compared to iron sucrose. No patients reported being dissatisfied in either group. (Figure-8) [27]

Figure-8: Patient's Satisfaction with Treatment

CONCLUSION

This study compared the efficacy, safety, and patient satisfaction of Ferric Carboxymaltose (FCM) and Iron Sucrose in the management of iron-deficiency anemia, particularly among pregnant women. Both treatments were effective in improving hemoglobin levels and alleviating symptoms; however, FCM demonstrated a slightly better clinical profile. Patients receiving FCM experienced faster hemoglobin improvement, fewer adverse effects, and higher satisfaction rates, likely due to its single-dose convenience and better tolerability. Given its practical advantages, FCM may be considered a more efficient and patient-friendly option for anemia management, particularly in settings where follow-up and multiple infusions may be challenging. Further large-scale studies are recommended to strengthen the evidence base and support wider clinical use.

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